

**PREPARATION OF SUPRAMOLECULAR COMPLEXES
BASED ON MENTHOL DERIVATIVES****Z.T.Khalmuratova****Sh.N.Turemuratov,****Karakalpakstan Research Institute of Natural Sciences, Academy of
Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan****U.K.Abdurakhmanova****Gulistan State University****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19652650>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 14th April 2026Accepted: 16th April 2026Online: 18th April 2026**KEYWORDS***menthol, menthyl acetyl chloride,
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spectrum***ABSTRACT***This article reports the synthesis of new supramolecular complexes based on menthol acetyl chloride with glycyrrhizic acid in various molar ratios (2:1, 4:1, and 9:1). The physicochemical properties of the obtained complexes were investigated. The physicochemical parameters of the synthesized supramolecular compounds were studied, and their chemical structures were analyzed using IR spectroscopy methods.***Introduction**

Licorice root has been used as a medicinal remedy in traditional medicine since ancient times. It was already applied in ancient Chinese medicine as early as 2800 BC. It has mainly been recommended for the treatment of upper respiratory tract diseases, for relieving cough, and for managing colds [1]. In the works of Ibn Sina (Avicenna), licorice syrup is described as beneficial for wound healing, while its ointment is considered effective in the treatment of burns. Furthermore, it is characterized as an expectorant for respiratory tract diseases, a remedy for reducing throat pain, and a средство for improving voice clarity [2]. The main active component of licorice is glycyrrhizic acid (GA). Its molecule contains both hydrophilic and hydrophobic fragments, which enable it to form complex compounds with various biologically active substances, including prostaglandins, poorly water-soluble antibiotics, hydrocortisone, prednisolone, uracil, and nystatin. As a result, the toxicity of drugs can be reduced, their duration of action prolonged, and new pharmaceutical forms can be developed [3].

Menthol and its derivatives are widely and effectively used in medicine as components of numerous pharmaceutical preparations, as well as in the perfume and food industries. When applied to the skin, menthol produces a cooling effect and is therefore used as a soothing agent for headaches. It also exhibits antiseptic properties and is used in the treatment of inflammation of the nasal and throat mucosa, as well as being included in analgesic drugs and topical formulations [4]. The effects of menthol and other monoterpenes on membranes have been shown to occur through changes in the physicochemical properties of integral proteins (ion channels, transporters) and phospholipids, as well as through indirect modulation of channel function. The (-)-menthol isomer is included in formulations with strong cooling and refreshing effects, whereas the (+)-isomer exhibits similar properties

but differs by its bitter taste and lower activity. The cooling effect of (-)-menthol is approximately four times stronger than that of the (+)-isomer [5].

Chloroacetylation products are also of significant importance in various sectors of the economy. They are used as raw materials for the production of pharmaceuticals, stabilizers for polymerization reaction products, and pesticides for plant protection in agriculture [6]. Therefore, the synthesis of supramolecular complexes based on menthol and its derivatives, the identification of biologically active substances among them, and the development and implementation of technologies for producing effective pharmaceutical preparations based on these compounds represent one of the urgent challenges of modern science.

Preparation of Supramolecular complexes based on mentholacetylchloride and glycyrrhizic acid; Supramolecular complexes of synthesized menthol acetyl chloride with glycyrrhizic acid were obtained at different molar ratios (2:1, 4:1, and 9:1).

Here, n-2.4.9 R- NH₄, H

Scheme 1. Preparation of supramolecular complexes of menthol acetyl chloride with glycyrrhizic acid.

To obtain complexes with glycyrrhizic acid (GA), GA was first dissolved in 96% ethanol, after which a solution of menthol acetyl chloride in 50% ethanol was added. The reaction mixture was then intensively stirred at room temperature for 6–8 hours. Subsequently, ethanol was completely removed using a rotary evaporator, and the remaining aqueous phase was dried by lyophilization (freeze-drying). Since glycyrrhizic acid has good solubility, a 50% water–ethanol system was directly used during the complex formation process. Some physicochemical parameters of the obtained complexes were determined (Table 1).

Table-1

Some physicochemical parameters of supramolecular complexes of menthol acetyl chloride with glycyrrhizic acid

No	Complexes	Molar ratio	T.melting C ^o	Yield %
1	MAC : GA	1:2	196-200	84-85
2	MAC : GA	1:4	196-198	89-90
3	MAC : GA	1:9	206-208	97-98

As can be seen from the data presented in Table 1, all the complex compounds obtained with glycyrrhizic acid (GA) are readily soluble in water. Their yields are relatively high, ranging from 84% to 98%. The formation of the complexes was confirmed using IR spectroscopy methods

Conclusion

In conclusion, new supramolecular complexes were synthesized based on a novel menthol derivative—menthol acetyl chloride (MAC)—with glycyrrhizic acid (GA) at different molar ratios (2:1, 4:1, and 9:1). The obtained results demonstrated the following: all complexes were obtained in high yields (84–98%) and exhibited good water solubility. This indicates an increase in solubility despite the hydrophobic nature of MAC. Spectral analysis confirmed the formation of a supramolecular system due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding and electrostatic interactions between the host and guest molecules. Thus, stable supramolecular complexes of menthol acetyl chloride with GA at different molar ratios were obtained. Their physicochemical properties were characterized, and their structures were confirmed using optical spectroscopy methods.

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